

Stress and deformation analysis of circular tunnels with consideration of blast-induced damage and gravity

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ABSTRACT: Analysis of stresses and deformations around circular tunnels and shafts are critical for evaluation of the interaction between the support system and the ground and therefore the tunnel support design and stability. The damage induced in the material by the excavation method (i.e., blasting) can significantly influence the ground response as the excavation alters the rock mass properties over the damaged zone. When the provided support pressure inside the tunnel falls below a critical value, a zone of plastic (broken) material develops around the tunnel. The self-weight of the broken material is significant at the crown of the tunnel and may subject the support to larger stresses. This study presents a new analytical-numerical solution for the determination of stresses, strains, and deformations around a tunnel with the consideration of the gravity effect and the blast induced damaged zone. A modified equilibrium equation for the ground is used and the elastic and plastic zones of the tunnel are analyzed. The results indicate that gravity and the damaged zone have significant effect on the tunnel convergence. The presented method in this paper is novel and allows the tunnel designers to assess the combined effect of blasting quality and gravity in the tunnel convergence.

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to characterize the stresses and displacements around an excavation, it is necessary to understand the behavior of the rock mass around the tunnel. As excavation in an initially elastic rock mass occurs, the original properties of the rock mass are changed. Based on the method of excavation, the properties of the surrounding material can be influenced by the development of an excavation damaged or disturbed zone. The degree and extent of this damaged zone varies significantly based on the selected method of excavation. In tunnels excavated mechanically by TBM drilling, the effect of the damage in the surrounding rock mass is negligible. In the drill and blast method, the influence of excavation disturbance in the rock mass near the tunnel radius is far more significant (Martino and Chandler, 2004; Kwon et al. 2009; Bastante et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2017). Therefore, it is of interest to consider the effects of a blast-induced damaged zone (BIDZ) when analyzing the stresses and deformations around an excavation. The development of a BIDZ has a considerable effect on the strength and stiffness of the rock mass. This damage to the material is assumed to form a cylindrical zone of influence at a constant extent. The zone beyond the BIDZ is characterized by undamaged

material properties. Recently, geophysical techniques such as seismic wave propagation (Hedayat 2013; Hedayat et al., 2012; 2013; 2014a-d; 2018; Hedayat and Walton, 2017; Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018a-b) have been used to estimate the extent and quality of BIDZ (Day and Murthy, 2013). Hoek et al. (2002) introduced a factor accounting for degree of disturbance due to blast damage and stress redistribution, D . This disturbance factor depends directly on the quality of the blasting applied to the excavation, and is estimated based on the appearance of the rock mass. Based on D , associated properties of the damaged zone can be calculated using empirical equations.

Interaction between the ground and the support system requires determination of the ground response curve (GRC). GRC is the relation between the decreasing tunnel internal pressure and the increasing tunnel radial convergence and can be constructed from elasto-plastic analysis of a circular tunnel subjected to hydrostatic far-field stress and uniform internal pressure. A large body of work currently exists on the stress and deformation analysis of tunnels with the consideration of different failure criteria and rock mass behaviors including the elastic-perfectly plastic, elastic-brittle-plastic and elastic-strain-softening models (e.g., Brown et al., 1983; Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst, 1999; Carranza-Torres,

2004; Alonso et al., 2003; Park and Kim, 2006; Lee and Pietruszczak, 2008; Park et al., 2008; Fahimifar and Hedayat, 2008; 2009; Fahimifar et al., 2010; González-Caoa et al., 2013; Hedayat, 2016). When the internal pressure in tunnels falls below a critical pressure, p_{cr} , a plastic zone develops around the tunnel. The dead weight of this broken zone exerts higher pressures to the support system at the crown (roof) of the tunnel and needs to be considered in the elasto-plastic analysis of the tunnel.

The main objective of this study is to present a new analytical-numerical solution for the determination of stresses, strains, and deformations around a deep circular tunnel with the consideration of the gravity effect and the blast induced damaged zone. The modified equilibrium equation for the ground with the consideration of the gravity effect is used in this study and the stresses and deformations are obtained by considering the elastic, plastic, and damaged zones forming around the tunnel.

2. DEFINITION OF PROBLEM

The tunnel problem considered in this paper is shown in Figure 1. A deep circular tunnel in a continuous, homogeneous, isotropic, and initially elastic rock mass subjected to the hydrostatic far-field stress of p_0 is shown here. Because of the blasting impact, a cylindrical blast induced damaged zone (BIDZ) is developed around the tunnel with different material properties than the rest of the medium. For this tunnel problem, a uniform support pressure of p_i is assumed to act radially on the interior of the tunnel. As the internal pressure decreases, the tunnel radial convergence u_r increases. Ground reaction curve is by definition the relation between the decreasing internal support pressure and increasing ground convergence. When the radial internal pressure falls below a critical pressure, p_{cr} , a circular failure zone of radius R_p develops around the tunnel.

Fig. 1. Presentation of a deep circular tunnel subjected to a hydrostatic stress field with gravity effect and damaged zone development. u_r is the radial convergence, R_p is the plastic radius, and R_d is the radius of the damaged zone.

The rock mass is assumed to obey the generalized Hoek-Brown (H-B) failure criterion (Hoek et al., 2002) as the most widely applied failure criterion for prediction of the rock material behavior.

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_3 + \sigma_{ci} \left(\frac{m_b \sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^a \quad (1)$$

where σ_1 and σ_3 are the major and minor principal stresses, respectively. σ_{ci} is the unconfined compressive strength of the intact rock and m_b , s , and a are material constants related to the rock quality. The material constants can be estimated from the Geological Strength Index (GSI), the initial rock constant m_i , the disturbance factor D . The following equations provide the estimates for the H-B material constants:

$$m_b = m_i \exp\left(\frac{GSI-100}{28-14D}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$s = \exp\left(\frac{GSI-100}{9-3D}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$a = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6} \left[e^{\frac{-GSI}{15}} - e^{\frac{-20}{3}} \right] \quad (4)$$

D is a factor that depends upon the degree of disturbance to which the rock mass has been subjected by factors such as blast damage and stress relaxation (Hoek et al., 2002). The D factor varies from 0 for excellent quality-controlled blasting or excavation by Tunnel Boring Machines (TBM) with minimal disturbance to the in-situ rock mass to the value of 1 for rock masses with significant disturbance caused by heavy production blasting or poor blasting.

The value of GSI varies from 10 for extremely poor rock masses to 100 for intact rock masses. The strength parameter a is not a constant value as it was defined in H-B criterion developed in 1998. a varies from 0.5 for the excellent rock mass ($GSI=100$) to 0.66 for a very weak rock mass ($GSI=0$). Because this parameter a is not necessarily equal to 0.5, most of existing elasto-plastic solutions of circular tunnels in Hoek-Brown materials still assume the older version of the H-B criterion with $a=0.5$ for simplicity.

3. ROCK MASS YIELD CRITERION AND ROCK MODEL

For the case of a circular tunnel with axial-symmetric conditions, the state of stress at any distance r is defined by the radial stress, σ_r , and the tangential or circumferential stress, σ_θ . For the case of a long tunnel, the longitudinal stress is considered as the intermediate principal stress. Therefore, the radial stress is the minor

principal stress and the tangential stress is the major principal stress. Hence, equation 1 can be re-written as

$$\sigma_\theta = \sigma_r + \sigma_{ci} \left(\frac{m_b \sigma_r}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^a \quad (5)$$

When the rock mass yields, the peak H-B strength parameters σ_{ci} , m_b , s , and a reduce to lower values as a function of the assumed stress-strain model for the rock. The three common models of material behavior include elastic-plastic, elastic-brittle plastic, and elastic-strain softening. This study focuses on rocks with elastic-perfectly plastic and elastic-brittle plastic behavior and can be expanded to consider the elastic strain softening behavior. Figure 2 shows these two stress-strain models in terms of principal stress difference ($\sigma_1 - \sigma_3$), major principal (circumferential) strain, ε_1 , and minor principal (radial) strain, ε_3 .

For materials at the residual strength state, the H-B failure criterion can be written as:

$$\sigma_\theta = \sigma_r + \sigma_{cir} \left(\frac{m_r \sigma_r}{\sigma_{cir}} + s_r \right)^{a_r} \quad (6)$$

where σ_{cir} is the residual unconfined compressive strength for the rock, and m_r , s_r , and a_r are the residual H-B parameters. The blast induced damaged part of the plastic zone can also be characterized by the same H-B failure criterion (Eqs. (5-6)) but with different strength parameters with consideration of D factor in Eqs. (2-3). The strength parameters for the damaged zone are denoted by subscript 'D' and are as follows: σ_{cd} , m_{bd} , s_d , m_{rd} , and s_{rd} .

Fig. 2. (a) simplified stress-strain behavior for perfectly-plastic and brittle-plastic model applicable to damaged and plastic zones; and (b) flow rule for relating principal strains.

3.1. Plastic Potential Function

In analysis of tunnels, an appropriate plastic potential function needs to be defined. When the plastic potential function is similar to the failure (yield) criterion, the function is called associated flow rule. When the potential

function differs from the failure criterion, it is called non-associated flow rule. Several studies that dealt with dilation problem in rocks and rock masses recommended the use of non-associated flow rules in elasto-plastic analysis of tunnels. One of the most common non-associated flow rules used in conjunction with the H-B failure criterion is the Mohr-Coulomb potential function (Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst, 1999; Alonso et al., 2003; Carranza-Torres, 2004; Deb, 2006; Lee and Pietruszczak, 2008; Park et al., 2008) as follows:

$$Q = \sigma_\theta + \sigma_r K_\psi \quad (7)$$

where K_ψ is the coefficient of dilation and is defined as:

$$K_\psi = \frac{1 + \sin \psi}{1 - \sin \psi} \quad (8)$$

Brown et al. (1983) assumed that the dilation angle is a constant parameter within the plastic zone.

In the plastic zone, the total radial and tangential strains, ε_r and ε_θ , consist of elastic strains, ε_r^e and ε_θ^e , and plastic strains, ε_r^p and ε_θ^p . Using the above-mentioned non-associated flow rule and assuming that elastic strains are small compared to plastic strains, the relation between the major and minor principal strains will be as follows:

$$\varepsilon_r^p + K_\psi \varepsilon_\theta^p = 0 \quad (9)$$

3.2. Consideration of Gravity in the Equilibrium Equation

The weight of the broken zone around the tunnel can be so large that it may affect the tunnel stability. The most critical point is the crown (roof) of the tunnel and the stability assessment is carried out by the construction of the ground response curve at the roof. Detournay (1984) proposed a model for consideration of the body forces toward the center of an opening. In this model, the gravity loading is assumed to be directly inward to the tunnel center and the equilibrium equation within the broken is written as

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} + \gamma = 0 \quad (10)$$

where γ is the unit weight of the rock mass.

4. ANALYSIS OF STRESSES AND DEFORMATIONS IN THE ELASTIC ZONE

Assuming a state of plane strain and axial symmetry around the tunnel, the elastic solution given by Lamé (see Carranza-Torres, 2004) can be used to determine the stresses, strains, and the radial deformation within the elastic zone as follows:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = p_0 + (p_0 - p_{cr}) \left(\frac{R_p}{r} \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_r = p_0 - (p_0 - p_{cr}) \left(\frac{R_p}{r} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

$$\varepsilon_{\theta} = -\varepsilon_r = \frac{p_0 - p_{cr}}{2G} \left(\frac{R_p}{r} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

$$u_r = \frac{p_0 - p_{cr}}{2G} \frac{R_p^2}{r} \quad (14)$$

where p_{cr} is the critical stress and equivalent to the radial stress acting at the elastic-plastic interface (boundary). The term G is the shear modulus of the rock mass.

5. ANALYSIS OF STRESSES IN THE PLASTIC ZONE

At the elastic-plastic boundary, stress condition is such that a rock element is in equilibrium and no more yielding is occurring. In order to determine the radius of plastic zone, R_p , and the radial stress in the elastic-plastic interface, p_{cr} , the peak failure criterion of the rock mass, Eq. (5), must be satisfied at the boundary of the elastic zone. In other words, by substituting the tangential and radial stresses at elastic boundary, from Eqs. (11-12), into Eq. (5), the following equation can define the critical stress:

$$\sigma_{ci} \left(m_b \frac{p_{cr}}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^a - 2(p_0 - p_{cr}) = 0 \quad (15)$$

This equation can be solved by using numerical methods such as Newton-Raphson method. Only when the parameter a is equal to 0.5, this equation has an exact analytical solution as follows:

$$p_{cr} (a = 0.5) = p_0 - \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ci} \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{m_b}{4} \right)^2 + m_b \frac{p_0}{\sigma_{ci}} + s} - \frac{m_b}{8} \right)$$

For other cases when $a \neq 0.5$, the following equation can be used to obtain an accurate solution for the critical pressure:

$$p_{cr} = p_{cr} (a = 0.5) + \frac{2(p_0 - p_{cr}^{a=0.5}) - \sigma_{ci} \left(m_b \frac{p_{cr}^{a=0.5}}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^a}{2 + a m_b \left(m_b \frac{p_{cr}^{a=0.5}}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^{a-1}} \quad (17)$$

After determining the critical pressure, by substituting $\sigma_{\theta} - \sigma_r$, from Eq. (5) for the case of elastic-perfectly plastic and from Eq. (6) for the case of elastic-brittle plastic, into Eq. (10), the equilibrium equation may be expressed as:

$$\frac{d\sigma_r}{dr} - \frac{\sigma_{ci} \left(m_b \frac{\sigma_r}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^a}{r} + \gamma = 0 \quad (18)$$

This equation does not have an exact closed form analytical solution for σ_r in the plastic region. However, by using numerical solutions such as Runge-Kutta method, and boundary conditions of $\sigma_r = \sigma_r(R_D)$ at $r = R_D$ and $\sigma_r = p_{cr}$ at $r = R_p$, the radial stress in the plastic zone can be determined. For the damaged area of the plastic zone, the same procedure mentioned above can be repeated while using the damaged strength properties (i.e., σ_{cd} , m_{bd} , s_d , m_{rd} , s_{rd}) and the boundary conditions of $\sigma_r = \sigma_r(R_D)$ at $r = R_D$ and $\sigma_r = p_i$ at $r = r_o$.

6. ANALYSIS OF DEFORMATIONS IN THE PLASTIC ZONE

In order to define the relationship between plastic strain components and stress increments, an assumption must be made for the material behavior. The most general assumption is that the plastic strain rates are proportional to the stress gradient of plastic potential function, Q (Deb, 2006).

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_r^p = \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \sigma_r} d\eta; \quad \dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta}^p = \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \sigma_{\theta}} d\eta \quad (19)$$

where $d\eta$ is the plastic multiplier constant, $\dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta}^p$ and $\dot{\varepsilon}_r^p$ are plastic strain rates and Q is the plastic potential function that is very similar to the yield function.

Eliminating the plastic multiplier $d\eta$ in Eq. (19), the relation between radial and tangential strain rates is

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_r^p = A_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta}^p \quad (20)$$

where

$$A_1 = \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \sigma_r} \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \sigma_{\theta}} \right)^{-1} = -K_{\psi} \quad (21)$$

It is assumed that in the plastic region, total strain rates, $\dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta}$ and $\dot{\varepsilon}_r$, consist of elastic and plastic components:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_r = \dot{\varepsilon}_r^e + \dot{\varepsilon}_r^p \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta} = \dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta}^e + \dot{\varepsilon}_{\theta}^p \quad (23)$$

The relationships between the elastic components of strain rate and stress rate is given by Hooke's law. The plastic components of the strain rates are defined by the assumed plastic potential function. The following equations provide the strain rates for this analysis:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_r = \frac{\partial \dot{u}_r}{\partial r} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{\varepsilon}_\theta = \frac{\dot{u}_r}{r} \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_r^e = \frac{1}{2G} [(1-\nu)\dot{\sigma}_r - \nu\dot{\sigma}_\theta] \quad (25)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_\theta^e = \frac{1}{2G} [-\nu\dot{\sigma}_r + (1-\nu)\dot{\sigma}_\theta] \quad (26)$$

where the rates of all mechanical parameters, as denoted by a dot, refer to the first-order derivative with respect to the plastic radius. The parameter, ν , is the Poisson's ratio of the rock mass. Using Eqs. (22-26) with the consistency equation and the normalized radius $\rho = r/R_p$, the displacement discontinuity equation in the unit plane can be expressed as

$$\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \rho^2} - \frac{K_\psi}{\rho^2} u_r + \frac{K_\psi}{\rho} \frac{du_r}{d\rho} u_r - \frac{1}{2G} \times [(1-\nu - \nu K_\psi) \frac{d\sigma_r}{d\rho} - (\nu - (1-\nu)K_\psi) \frac{d\sigma_\theta}{d\rho}] = 0 \quad (27)$$

It is now necessary to define the boundary conditions required to numerically integrate the compatibility equation. Because the radial displacement is continuous on each side of the elasto-plastic interface, the displacement at the plastic side of the interface is equal to the displacement at the elastic one, as defined by Lamé (Jaeger and Cook, 2007).

$$u_r(\rho=1) = \frac{(p_0 - p_{cr})}{2G} R_p \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{du_r}{d\rho}(\rho=1) = -\frac{(p_0 - p_{cr})}{2G} R_p \quad (29)$$

For the rock mass with elastic-brittle plastic behavior, due to the sudden drop in the strength parameters in the plastic region, there is a discontinuity of strength on each side of the elastic-plastic interface. Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (1999) provided the following equation to define the first derivative of the radial displacement with respect to the variable ρ .

$$\frac{du_r}{d\rho}(\rho=1) = -K_\psi u_r(1) + \frac{(p_{cr} - p_0)}{2G} R_p (1 - 2\nu - 2\nu K_\psi + K_\psi) - \frac{R_p}{2G} \sigma_{cir} (\nu - K_\psi + \nu K_\psi) \left(\frac{p_{cr} m_r}{\sigma_{cir}} + s_r \right)^{a_r} \quad (30)$$

7. EFFECT OF BIDZ AND GRAVITY OF THE ELASTO-PLASTIC ANALYSIS

Ground-support interaction and determination of the tunnel convergence and the applied pressure to the support system are among the main applications of the

presented elasto-plastic analysis. To demonstrate the application of the proposed solution and to document the importance of the gravity effect and the BIDZ extent, the following tunnel case with the listed properties in Table 1 is analyzed and discussed in this section.

This excavation is a circular tunnel excavated in poor quality rock mass (GSI=27) with elastic-perfectly plastic behavior. The H-B parameters for the damaged zone are functions of the assumed D value for the tunnel and are determined according to Eqs. (2-4). The extent of the damaged zone, R_D , in this example is assumed to be equal to half of the extent of the plastic zone. In other words, $R_D = r_o + 1/2(R_p - r_o)$. In this case, the internal pressure may range from the critical stress value of 1.31 MPa for this tunnel to the support pressure of zero. For these different internal pressure values, the extent of the plastic zone, R_p , is determined.

Table 1. Tunnel and rock properties

Properties	Tunnel case (Brown et al., 1983)
Young's Modulus, E (MPa) (Hoek et al., 2002)	1245.8
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.25
Radius of opening, r_o (m)	5.35
Initial stress, p_0 (MPa)	3.31
Dilation angle, ψ (degree)	0
γ (kN / m^3)	27
GSI	25
m_{intact}	8
$\sigma_c = \sigma_{cir}$ (MPa)	27.6
$m_b = m_r$	0.55
$s_b = s_r$	0.00024
$a = a_r$	0.5312
D	0, 0.5, 0.7, 0.8, 1.0

Figure 3 shows the ground reaction curves for this tunnel with no consideration of the gravity effect (Fig. 3a) and with consideration of the gravity effect (Fig. 3b). As the D value increases, the tunnel convergence for the same value of the internal pressure increases, as expected.

For the case with consideration of the gravity effect, the tunnel deformations are significantly higher than the case with no consideration of the gravity effect (ignoring the weight of the broken rock mass in the plastic zone). Interestingly enough, for the cases with D values of 0.8 and 1.0 and with consideration of gravity, the tunnel becomes unstable for the internal pressures below 0.05 MPa and 0.15 MPa, respectively. In other words, no exact amount of convergence can be obtained for the unsupported tunnels with D values of 0.8 and higher.

(a) GRC with no consideration of gravity effect

(b) GRC with consideration of gravity effect

Fig. 3. Ground Reaction Curves for the tunnel with variable D values.

Figure 4 shows the relation between the applied internal pressure and the resulting normalized plastic radii (R_p/r_0). A comparison between the results of this study with and without consideration of the gravity effect is also made. In the case of no gravity consideration for an unsupported tunnel (i.e., $p_i=0$ MPa), the plastic radius extends to about 3.68 times the tunnel radius. With the gravity effect, the internal pressure reaches a minimum value of 0.12 MPa, below which the plastic radius becomes infinite and consequently the tunnel becomes unstable. In other words, the existence of a minimum in Figure 4 for this tunnel with gravitational effects indicates the onset of instability. The minimum occurs as the dead weight of the material in the broken zone above the tunnel increases in relative importance compared to the loads involved in the equilibrium balance.

Fig. 4. The extent of plastic zone as a function of the internal stress with and without consideration of gravity effects.

A comparison between the GRC curves with and without consideration of the gravity effect and the BIDZ zone is considered in Figure 5. As seen, for the tunnel excavated by tunnel boring machines or mechanical excavation (no blasting) with $D=0$ (i.e., no BIDZ development), the GRC curves with and without consideration of gravity are very similar and project similar stress-convergence trends. However, for the tunnel with production blasting or poor blasting with the D value of 1, the GRC curves show a significantly higher convergence. The model with consideration of the gravity effect predicts an unstable tunnel when left unsupported.

Fig. 5. Combined effect of gravity and BIDZ on GRC curves.

To consider the effect of R_D on the radial convergence (displacement) of the tunnel, the tunnel with properties listed in Table 1 is considered. The internal support pressure is assumed to be 0.25 MPa and the D value is assumed to be equal to 1. The gravity effect is also considered in this analysis. The dimensionless radial convergence, u_r/r_0 (%) as a function of the normalized radii is plotted in Fig. 6 for cases with $R_D=5.35$ m (tunnel radius); $R_D=7$ m; and $R_D=9$ m.

Fig. 6. Dimensionless radial displacement with the effect of the damaged plastic zone.

The radius of the damaged zone plays a significant role on radial convergence in the tunnel. Measurement of the extent of the damaged zone in a tunnel is difficult. Given its significance in the convergence of the tunnel based on this analysis, it is suggested to perform parametric studies during the early design stage of the tunnel to evaluate the ground convergence for different scenarios.

CONCLUSIONS

A new analytical-numerical solution for elasto-plastic analysis of deep circular tunnels excavated in the generalized Hoek-Brown rock masses is presented in this study. This new solution takes into consideration the effect of blasting on the rock mass quality (i.e., radius of damaged zone and the degree of disturbance) as well as the weight of the broken rock mass within the plastic zone. This study demonstrates that the blast-induced damaged zone and gravity both can significantly influence the stresses and displacements in the rock mass. The presented solution in this paper is novel and allows tunnel engineers to assess the effect of blasting quality on the ground and support interaction in tunnels.

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